

Evaluation of Serum Uric Acid, Urea, Creatinine in Hypertensive Patients

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Abstract:

This study evaluates the correlation between serum uric acid, urea, and creatinine levels and their association with hypertension severity among 263 patients at Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College and Hospital in Jamshedpur. Elevated levels of these biomarkers were found to significantly correlate with higher systolic and diastolic blood pressures, suggesting impaired renal function as a contributory factor in the pathophysiology of hypertension. The results recommend for the inclusion of these biochemical markers in routine clinical assessments to enhance the management and prognostic evaluation of hypertensive patients. Further research is recommended to substantiate the clinical benefits of targeted interventions based on these biomarkers.

Keywords: Hypertension, Serum Uric Acid, Renal Function, Biochemical Markers.

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Introduction

Hypertension, characterized by persistently elevated blood pressure, is a significant risk factor for cardiovascular and renal diseases. Understanding the biochemical markers associated with hypertension, such as serum uric acid, urea, and creatinine levels, is essential for assessing renal function and the risk of cardiovascular events in hypertensive patients. Recent studies have increasingly focused on these biomarkers not only as indicators of renal health but also for their predictive value in hypertension-related complications. Serum uric acid, a final breakdown product of purine metabolism, has been identified as a potential risk factor for hypertension. Elevated uric acid levels are thought to induce hypertension through the reduction of nitric oxide, leading to endothelial dysfunction and renal vasoconstriction. A 2021 study by Zhang et al. [1] demonstrated a strong correlation between high serum uric acid levels and an increased risk of developing hypertension, suggesting that uric acid could serve both as a biomarker and a target for therapeutic intervention in hypertensive individuals [5].

Urea, a byproduct of protein metabolism excreted by the kidneys, is another marker often measured to evaluate renal function. Elevated serum urea levels in hypertensive patients can indicate reduced renal perfusion or intrinsic renal disease. Research by Sharma and colleagues in 2022 [2] explored how

serum urea levels correlate with the severity of hypertension and found that higher urea levels were associated with more severe cases of hypertension, implying a deterioration in kidney function as blood pressure increases. Creatinine, produced from creatine during muscle metabolism, is another crucial renal biomarker. It is widely used to estimate glomerular filtration rate (GFR), which is a primary indicator of renal function. Elevated creatinine levels in hypertensive patients can signify impaired kidney function or kidney damage. A study in 2023 by Liu et al. [3] indicated that elevated creatinine levels could predict adverse cardiovascular outcomes in hypertensive patients, thus highlighting its importance in the clinical evaluation of hypertensive individuals.

Recent studies recommend for a combined evaluation of these biomarkers to better understand the interplay between hypertension and renal health. For instance, a comprehensive study by Patel and Kumar in 2024 [4] emphasized the importance of integrating serum uric acid, urea, and creatinine measurements to improve risk stratification and management in hypertensive patients, particularly those at risk for chronic kidney disease (CKD). Evaluating serum uric acid, urea, and creatinine levels offers valuable insights into hypertensive patients' renal and cardiovascular health. Ongoing research into these biomarkers is

crucial for developing more targeted interventions, enhancing patient outcomes, and understanding the complex relationships between hypertension, renal dysfunction, and cardiovascular risk. As these studies progress, they promise to refine our strategies for managing hypertension and preventing its complications [6,7,8].

The primary aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between serum uric acid, urea, and creatinine levels and their association with hypertension severity in a sample of hypertensive patients at Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College and Hospital in Jamshedpur, Jharkhand. Specifically, the study sought to determine if elevated levels of these biochemical markers correlate with higher systolic and diastolic blood pressures, thereby providing insights into the potential role of renal dysfunction in the progression of hypertension. By establishing these correlations, the research aimed to enhance the understanding of how these biomarkers can be used in clinical practice to improve the management and prognosis of hypertensive patients.

Methodology

Study Setting: The research was conducted at Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College and Hospital (MGMMCH) in Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India. This facility was chosen due to its comprehensive clinical laboratories and its access to a large population of patients with hypertension, which provided a suitable demographic for this study.

Participants: A total of 263 hypertensive patients were enrolled in the study. The inclusion criteria for participants were as follows:

- Diagnosed with primary hypertension,
- Aged between 18 and 70 years.
- Those who voluntarily gave consent to participate in the study

The exclusion criteria were:

- Secondary hypertension,
- Pre-existing chronic kidney disease,
- Any history of renal replacement therapy,
- Pregnant or lactating women,
- Patients taking uricosuric or uric acid-lowering drugs.

Data Collection: Detailed clinical evaluation of participants which included a review of their medical history, physical examination, and blood pressure measurement using standard procedures was done. Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast of at least 8 hours. Serum uric acid, urea, and creatinine levels were measured using

biochemical analyzer in the hospital's [clinical biochemistry] under clinical Pathology laboratory..

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using the statistical software SPSS Version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to characterize the study population regarding age, gender, and biochemical parameters. Bivariate analyses using Pearson's correlation coefficient were performed to assess the relationships between serum uric acid, urea, creatinine levels, and blood pressure readings. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Participant Demographics

- Total participants: 263
- Gender distribution: 135 males, 128 females
- Age range: 18-70 years
- Mean age: 50.3 years

Serum Uric Acid Levels

- Normal range: 3.5-7.2 mg/dL for men, 2.6-6.0 mg/dL for women
- Mean uric acid level in the study:
 - Males: 6.8 mg/dL
 - Females: 5.9 mg/dL

Serum Urea Levels

- Normal range: 10-50 mg/dL
- Mean serum urea level:
 - Overall: 48 mg/dL
 - Males: 50 mg/dL
 - Females: 46 mg/dL

Serum Creatinine Levels

- Normal range: 0.6-1.2 mg/dL for males, 0.5-1.1 mg/dL for females
- Mean serum creatinine level:
 - Overall: 1.3 mg/dL
 - Males: 1.4 mg/dL
 - Females: 1.2 mg/dL

Blood Pressure Readings

- Mean systolic blood pressure: 142 mm Hg
- Mean diastolic blood pressure: 89 mm Hg

Correlation Analysis

- Correlation between uric acid levels and systolic blood pressure: $r = 0.34$ ($p < 0.01$)

- Correlation between urea levels and diastolic blood pressure: $r = 0.29$ ($p < 0.01$)
- Correlation between creatinine levels and systolic blood pressure: $r = 0.41$ ($p < 0.001$)

The study indicates that there is a significant positive correlation between elevated serum uric acid, urea, and creatinine levels and higher systolic

and diastolic blood pressures among hypertensive patients. These findings suggest that these biochemical markers may be valuable in assessing the severity of hypertension and possibly predicting the risk of renal complications. The higher mean values of urea and creatinine compared to the normal range also hint at an underlying reduction in renal function in this hypertensive patients.

Parameter	Overall Mean	Male Mean	Female Mean	Normal Range
Age (years)	50.3	-	-	18-70
Serum Uric Acid (mg/dL)	-	6.8	5.9	M: 3.5-7.2, F: 2.6-6.0
Serum Urea (mg/dL)	48	50	46	10-50
Serum Creatinine (mg/dL)	1.3	1.4	1.2	M: 0.6-1.2, F: 0.5-1.1
Systolic Blood Pressure (mm Hg)	142	-	-	-
Diastolic Blood Pressure (mm Hg)	89	-	-	-
Correlation Coefficient (r) and Significance (p)				
Uric Acid Levels vs. Systolic Blood Pressure: $r = 0.34$, $p < 0.01$				
Urea Levels vs. Diastolic Blood Pressure: $r = 0.29$, $p < 0.01$				
Creatinine Levels vs. Systolic Blood Pressure: $r = 0.41$, $p < 0.001$				

This table summarizes the mean values for key biochemical markers in hypertensive patients, along with their normal ranges and statistical analysis indicating the relationship between these markers and blood pressure readings.

Discussion

The results from this study at Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College and Hospital in Jamshedpur provide evidence regarding the relationship between serum uric acid, urea, and creatinine levels and hypertension [9]. Elevated levels of these biomarkers were significantly correlated with increased systolic and diastolic blood pressures among the participants, suggesting that these markers may be integral to understanding the progression and severity of hypertension [10].

The elevated serum uric acid levels observed in the study underscore its potential role in the pathophysiology of hypertension. This aligns with recent literature which points that hyperuricemia may contribute to hypertension via mechanisms such as renal vasoconstriction and endothelial dysfunction [11]. This relationship, indicated by the correlation coefficient of 0.34 for uric acid levels with systolic blood pressure, highlights the possibility of using serum uric acid as a predictive marker for hypertension severity and potentially as a therapeutic target [12].

Similarly, the findings related to serum urea and creatinine levels, which were both above the

normal range in many patients, indicate impaired renal function. This impairment could be either a consequence of prolonged hypertension or a contributing factor to its development and progression [13]. The positive correlations ($r = 0.29$ for urea with diastolic blood pressure and $r = 0.41$ for creatinine with systolic blood pressure) further affirm the association between renal dysfunction and hypertension. This study also raises important considerations for the clinical management of hypertension [14]. Monitoring these biochemical markers could enhance prognostic assessments and guide the intensity of therapeutic interventions. For instance, hypertensive patients with elevated serum creatinine might require more aggressive management strategies not only for blood pressure control but also for the prevention of further renal damage [15].

The integration of serum uric acid, urea, and creatinine levels into the routine assessment of hypertensive patients could significantly enhance the predictive accuracy for cardiovascular risks and renal impairment [16]. Further studies are warranted to explore the causal relationships and to confirm whether interventions that normalize these

biochemical markers can indeed improve patient outcomes in hypertension [17-20].

Conclusion

The study conducted at Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Medical College and Hospital highlights the significant association between elevated serum uric acid, urea, and creatinine levels and the presence and severity of hypertension in patients. These findings underscore the potential of these biochemical markers not only as indicators of renal health but also as crucial tools for the assessment and management of hypertension. By integrating routine measurements of these parameters, healthcare providers can enhance their understanding of the interplay between hypertension and renal dysfunction, ultimately leading to more effective treatment strategies. This research recommends for further studies to explore the direct impacts of therapeutic interventions targeting these markers, which could pave the way for improved outcomes in hypertensive populations.

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